

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CELLS ARE THE SOLELY REACTIVE STRUCTURES ORIGINATING INTERNAL DRIVING FORCES OF ORGANISM'S ADAPTATION TO EXTERNAL/INTERNAL SHIFTS

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Abstract

Current presentations about the dynamics of human somatic health parameters (SHP) are too scarce to be used to diagnose and effectively cure non-trivial multifactor pathologies often accompanying aging. This theoretical article argues that originators of SHP's dynamics are internal driving forces (IDF) appearing due to cells' passive or active adaptation to induced energy imbalance (IEI). IEI appears under the low synthesis of ATP molecules or their inadequate high expenditures and suppresses the cell metabolism. This concentrates on two types of specific cytoplasmic interim chemicals also known as adaptation factors (AF1s and AF2s). AF1s penetrate the nucleus and correct the expression of genes responsible for certain metabolic transformations. This is the intracellular negative feedback (INF) with the main targets of mitochondria and ribosomes. AF2s, mainly appearing during extreme IEI, leave the cell and circulate with body liquids. Some of the AF2s act in local tissues and alter vascular parameters. Target cells of other AF2s are located in organs and functional systems that provide chemical income to cells or purify their cytoplasm. This is the multicellular mechanism (MM) enhancing the effect of INF. Due to the combined efforts of INF and MM, every cell dynamically self-tunes its organelles. These cellular reconstructions reconfigure the previously existing gradients of nutrient concentration thus under a general lack of nutrients, cells with lower assimilation power eventually fall into the state of IEI. Conclusions: 1) the cell is both the receptor of environmental alterations and the structural unit capable of adaptive responding to them; 2) individual adaptive self-tunings of cells alter the existing concentrations and originate IDF of those adaptation phenomena that were observed in experiments and described at the scales of organs and entire organism; 3) with revealing the nature of IDF medics can create effective technologies for control of adaptation's IDFs.

Keywords: cell, mitochondria, cellular life support system, integrative physiology, neural-hormonal control, hypertension.

1. Introduction

Adaptability to environmental changes is one of the most fundamental properties of each organism. Not least due to this property, species have survived and evolved. In humans, evolution has accumulated many mechanisms and ways of individual adaptive response to exogenous and endogenous shifts. Empirical physiology tries to comprehend these mechanisms, but the methodology does not track the changes simultaneously occurring at the subcellular, cellular, organ, and organismal levels in response to changes in the physicochemical characteristics of the environment. Therefore, modern empirical physiology of individual adaptation is more likely a set of data describing the surface level of the phenomenon by using a sequence of transformations of a small number of biological parameters than a coherent concept [1-4]. Considering that small variations in environmental parameters often cause significant changes in the dynamics and final state of the organism, the accumulated information cannot be used in applied physiology or medicine. There is undoubtedly a need for a critical rethinking of the problem and mechanisms of individual adaptation of a multicellular organism (in particular, a human organism) to endogenous/exogenous shifts. This rethinking is the goal of this article.

2. The key statements

Four key statements underline the fundamental novelty of the proposed approach to the problem of adaptation:

1. Every adaptation is a process that has its internal driving forces. Without understanding the nature of these driving forces, the conditions of their emergence, dynamics, and disappearance, it is hopeless to comprehend the phenomenon of adaptation;

2. Since single-celled organisms have adaptive properties, it is reasonable to assume that our cells are also adaptive. This indicates that the internal driving forces of cell adaptation to local environmental shifts are so small that precision measurements are required to detect and record them;

3. The typical empirical research of individual adaptation uses standard statistical methods that level out most nuances unfolding inside cells and in the local intercellular environment. In the context of the problem under consideration, the principal disadvantage of the method is that statistical processing "kills" small fluctuations in the internal driving forces of adaptation. Thus the researcher cannot notice the true cause of cellular adaptive restructuring but is mainly focused on a description of structural-functional alterations in organs and systems. This is why dominant theories of adaptation mistakenly believe that the organs and functional systems of the body provide active adaptation;

4. In a human organism, the cell is the lowest structural-functional element actively adapting its biochemistry and physiology to conditions that cannot be avoided.

3. Types of a cell adaptation to the altered conditions of local environment

To distinguish forms of cellular adaptation to the altered environment, it is worth to analyze why the adaptation is needed.

3.1. *The vulnerability of biological macromolecules is a fundamental flaw of life*

Most biological macromolecules are tertiary or quaternary structures sensitive to changes in the physicochemical parameters of the environment. Even little thermodynamic fluctuations break intermolecular bonds therefore the cell is forced to provide adequate re-synthesis. This fundamental drawback of cellular life played a crucial role in the evolution of special mechanisms compensating for the negative effects of molecular destruction [5]. Long life in unstable and often unfavorable conditions contributed to the survival of those unicellular organisms which armed mechanisms that made life possible despite this irreparable flaw.

Theoretically, two scenarios are possible for this: 1) the assortment and concentrations of source components in the cytoplasm are sufficient to provide the needed rate of compensatory biosynthesis; 2) under lack of resource(s) for compensatory biosynthesis, special mechanisms minimize the rate of molecular decay (e.g., turning into a spore state). During life evolution, both scenarios are realized but the transition to the spore state is observed only in primitive organisms. Cells of higher organisms currently alive use alternative adaptation mechanisms. Among them, the mechanisms of passive adaptation (MPA) and mechanisms of active adaptation (MAA) stand out. Without details, the fundamental differences between MPA and MAA are considered below.

3.2. *Passive adaptation*

MPA collects alternative biochemical mechanisms providing life in primary one-celled organisms despite the non-regular presence of due concentrations of certain nutrients. Therefore the cells that acquired additional chemical mechanisms (based on the transforming multiple nutrients for energetic or structural needs) were successfully passed through the sieve of evolution. The main disadvantage of MPA is the need to create and maintain these mechanisms decreasing the biological efficiency. An additional disadvantage of MPA is in the lowering of the net effect when several components of the entire mechanism cannot work. This last aspect may be illustrated using the complex mechanism of ATP synthesis in aerobic cells. Under oxygen lack, the aerobic cell uses the mechanism of anaerobic glycolysis producing two molecules of ATP from every glucose molecule. Pyruvate is another product of this mechanism. In the presence of oxygen, pyruvate enters the mitochondria and provides an additional synthesis of 16 ATP molecules. So, though the cell metabolism continues in the absence of oxygen, the rate of the metabolism is almost eight times less efficient. Perhaps, energy efficiency was the main factor that provided wide dissemination of aerobic organisms including their use in multicellular organisms. It is worth noting

that the passiveness of MPA suggests that internal recombining is always automatic and practically immediate.

3.3. *Reactive adaptation*

In contrast with MPA, MAA is an inertial mechanism and for its realization needs additional biosynthetic transformations requiring energy and substrates. Despite this obvious disadvantage, most aerobic cells have accumulated multiple MAA. To illustrate the characteristic aspect of MAA, let us use the same sample of ATP synthesis. Under chronic energy lack, specific intermitted chemicals (like hypoxia-inducible factors Hif1) eventually accumulate in the cytoplasm and penetrate the nucleus. There they alter (activate/deactivate) the expression of certain genes intensifying mitochondrial proliferation and fusion. Certainly, both mitochondrial re-arrangements require additional materials and need some time.

This basic version of MAA working against chronic energy lack in unicellular aerobic organisms has been acquired by multicellular organisms including mammals armed with multiple multicellular mechanisms enhancing the efficiency of the intracellular mechanism of reactive increasing (decreasing) the total rate of ATP synthesis. To identify these enhancers, the concept of two virtual cells was proposed [6].

4. The concept of two virtual cells

The adult human organism consists of about 50 trillion cells each belonging to one of 220 types. They all are competing for common resources. This is the fundamental and limiting factor of dynamics in events associated with the adaptive re-arrangements in cells, organs, and the entire organism. Empirical biology has no technology for discovering causal mechanisms determining the role of cellular adaptive re-arrangements in dynamics of physiological or pathological transformations observed at levels of organs and the entire organism. In fairness, it should be noted that changes in intracellular concentration gradients are so insignificant that they require super-sensitive instruments to register them. The special concept of two virtual cells (CTVC) [6] mainly overcomes this empirical obstacle.

The essence of CTVC is in the assumption that for every time moment, cells of the organism can be virtually subdivided into two types: the first virtual cell has no metabolic problem and is only a consumer of common substrates; the metabolism of the second virtual cell is suppressed because of energy or substrates lack, contaminated cytoplasm, others. In cases of a minimal number of second-type cells, the organism's biophysical and physiological parameters have minimal (basal) values. In parallel with increasing the amount of problematic cells, these parameters grow. This concept explains fluctuations and shifts of most biological characteristics (like arterial pressure, heart rate, blood chemistry, and body temperature) under alterations in mental and physical activities.

5. Interaction of intracellular and multicellular MAAs

Nuances in mechanisms providing the successive phases of activation or deactivation of specific DNA sites by specific substances are omitted. The operation of these mechanisms is schematically illustrated in pic. 1.

Pic. 1 Schematic illustration of CTVC explaining slow dynamics of body parameters. VC located in the left corner has a sufficient metabolic rate ($V_m \geq V_{m0}$), while VC in the center has a suppressed metabolic rate ($V_m < V_{m0}$). The cardiovascular system (CVS) is the mandatory participant in the adaptive responses of organs and systems that materially support intracellular remodeling.

According to CTVC, the organism is conventionally presented as a system of two virtual cells with different metabolic statuses. The first virtual cell presents all real cells provided with due metabolism. These cells are only consumers of common resources. The second virtual cell presents the real cells whose metabolism is insufficient to provide biological work. So, the latter cells try to activate the expression of genes responsible for energy and material providing of cell life. The active strategy of cell adaptation to worsened conditions of existence is based on negative feedback: the expression of certain genes depends on concentrations of specific chemical substances in the cytoplasm. Many such substances are discovered in various specialized cells of our body [7,8]. They are generally called adaptation factors (AFs). Perhaps it is not superfluous to list several well-known AFs: VEGF (vascular growth endothelial factor), and HIFs (hypoxia-inducible factors). Most of the so-called specific chemical regulators (angiotensin II, NO, erythropoietin, others) are also adaptation factors involved in complex responses of organisms to induced unfavorable conditions. This view helps to understand the role of so-called local (produced in brain, heart, liver, muscles) renin-angiotensin systems. Such a re-focusing of the adaptation phenomenon from organs and functional systems to every cell accentuates that current levels of specific gene expression control the synthesis and current concentrations of biopolymers to be used by cells for building and maintaining their organelles. If circumstances lead to the accumulation of an excess amount of a given biopolymer, it or an agent associated with the biopolymer, penetrating the cell nucleus, reduces the expression of genes that control the production of a given polymer. This negative feedback

also works in the opposite direction: when the concentration of a given polymer falls, the expression of the control genes increases. This mechanism effectively meets the cell's needs for consumables, if only initial substrates exist in the cytoplasm. Alternatively, activation of additional mechanisms that can increase the influx of ingredients necessary for the adequate compensatory synthesis of missing polymers is required. Possible scenarios and multicellular mechanisms that are involved in supplying the cell with ingredients for biosynthesis are considered in [6,9].

6. Biochemical negative feedbacks providing cell energy balance

In general, biochemical negative feedbacks providing cell energy balance are based on the concentration ratios of ADP/ATP and AMP/ATP. The decrease of ATP accelerates its synthesis via increase of cytoplasmic concentration of ADP. Effects of the same direction occur under a decrease of ADP: the velocity of AMP synthesis, using mitochondrial concentrations of pyruvate and oxygen, elevates. These two biochemical negative feedbacks are the most fast-acting autonomous mechanisms trying to balance the mean rates of energy synthesis ($v_s(\tau)$) with the mean rates of energy consumption ($v_c(\tau)$) within every time interval of τ . However, the efficiency of this mechanism decreases with increasing of $\Delta v_c(\tau)$. Thus let us analyze other regulators too.

Theoretically $v_s(\tau)$ is a function of the following variables:

$S_s(t)$ – characterizes the summary surface of internal membranes of cell mitochondria; $C_{Py}(t)$ – represents the pyruvate concentration; $C_{O_2}(t)$ – represents the oxygen concentration; $C_{P_i}(t)$ – represents the concentration of inorganic phosphor; $C_N(t)$ – represents the concentration of *NADH*.

Within short-time intervals of τ , $S_s(t) \approx const$. $C_{Py}(t)$ depends on $v_s(t)$ and pyruvate incomes depending on the cytoplasmic concentration of glucose and other carbohydrates. Oxygen incomes, depending on $P_aO_2(t)$ and local blood flow, elevate $C_{O_2}(t)$ while the increase of $v_s(t)$ decreases $C_{O_2}(t)$. Elevations of the gradient between the mean pressures in aortic arch (MAP) and central vena (CVP) increase the cardiac output (CO), while increases in the total ($R(t)$) decrease CO. Regional vascular resistances ($r(t)$) distribute CO to organs. Farther localization of flows depends on nuances of microvasculature nets. At the microscopic scale of a cell colony, each cell takes nutrients using their concentration gradients between the liquid intercellular environment and cell cytoplasm.

This formalization suggests that for every $S_s(t) \approx const$, under certain values of involved characteristics, the current value of $v_s(t)$ is a part of its theoretical maximum ($V_s(t)$). So, multiple mechanisms capable of altering blood flow can modulate the cell energy status. In other words, the intracellular rearrangements for elevation of $v_s(t)$ have at least a hemodynamic extracellular enhancer. It is effective until the arterial blood contains the required concentrations of carbohydrates and oxygen. Under their lack, other ways must be activated. These additional potential enhancers are considered below.

6.1. Ways for compensating the oxygen lack

It is well-known that normally an essential amount of erythrocytes is deposited in spleen and liver. Their mobilization into the active circulation helps to provide the organs actually having a higher metabolism. So, under energy scarce caused by oxygen lack reflector constrictions of spleen and liver can add to circulation a certain number of oxygen carriers – erythrocytes. An increase of the velocity of lung ventilation ($v_L(t)$) is another independent mechanism potentially capable of fast elevating $C_{O_2}(t)$. At last, an increase of erythropoiesis is the third though slow elevator of $C_{O_2}(t)$. Activators of this mechanism known as hypoxia inducible factors (HIF's) are already revealed [11,12].

It is well-known that under physiological norm an essential amount of erythrocytes is deposited in the spleen and liver. Therefore, organs sharply increasing their metabolism can be provided additional oxygen through portions of erythrocytes mobilized from their

depots. So, under energy scarcity caused by oxygen lack reflector constrictions of the spleen and liver can add to circulation a certain number of oxygen carriers – erythrocytes.

An increase in the velocity of lung ventilation ($v_L(t)$) is another independent mechanism capable of fast elevating $C_{O_2}(t)$. Reflector mechanisms based on chemoreceptors sensing blood *pH*, $PaCO_2$, and PaO_2 and controlling $C_{O_2}(t)$ are well-known. It is worth to stress here that both peripheral and central chemoreflexes also are altering MAP [2,7].

At last, an increase of erythropoiesis is the third though slow elevator of $C_{O_2}(t)$. Activators of this mechanism known are HIFs. Their role is essential under chronic local or regional ED caused by oxygen lack too.

6.2. Ways for compensating the glucose lack

The lack of carbohydrates finally transforming into glucose and pyruvate is an independent originator of ATP lack. Even in the background of the functionality of mitochondria and a sufficient amount of oxygen, the lack of glucose slows the metabolism down. Therefore, a search for mechanisms capable of compensating or mitigating this negative biological effect is argued. The empirical physiology mainly accentuated problems associated with diabetes and mechanisms of pancreas-liver interactions regulating blood concentrations of glucose, insulin, glycogen, and glucagon [13]. Despite investigations showing glucagon's influence on CO [14], the energetic aspect of this factor remains unclear yet.

At the cell scale, glucose lack firstly decreases the concentration of AMP. Multiple investigations revealed cell-scale and organism-scale compensatory responses to this situation. The main pathways are associated with AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) [15]. When activated by nutrient deficiency, AMPK stimulates glucose uptake and lipid oxidation to produce energy, while shutting down energy-consuming processes, including glucose and lipid production, to restore energy balance. AMPK acts as a sensor of internal adenosine phosphate levels and inhibits energy consumption pathways, and supports energy glycolysis and glycogenolysis) [16]. Exercise leads to the activation of AMPK in skeletal muscle, in abdominal adipose tissue, liver, and other organs. In addition to its normal role as an intracellular energy switch or fuel sensor, new research has shown that AMPK is a redox sensor and modulator that plays a key role in maintaining cardiovascular processes and inhibiting disease progression. In response to stressors that increase AMP levels in cells of the arterial wall, AMPK lowers blood pressure, but the effect of hyperlipidemia on this response has not been studied. Relatives of AMPK are found in essentially all eukaryotes, and it may have evolved to allow the host cell to monitor the output of the newly acquired mitochondria and step their ATP production up or down according to the demand [17,18].

6.3. Ways for increasing local (regional) hemodynamics without elevation of MAP

Elevation of perfusion pressure is not the exclusive way to increase local or regional hemodynamics. Under sufficient concentration of blood nutrients, vasodilation is among first line ways effectively minimizing up to middle severity acute lack of cell incomes. This opportunity is well-known in skeletal muscles, internal organs, and skin. Multiple endogenous vasodilator agents, increasing blood flow into tissues that need oxygen, glucose, lipids, and other nutrients, are known (adenosine, epinephrine, nitric oxide, prostaglandin, histamine, natriuretic peptides, hypoxia-inducible factors Hif1 α , Hif1 β , and others). However, under a big number of ED-cells, because of TPR's, and MAP's lowering, the efficiency of the vasodilation decreases. Under continuous regional ED, in addition to vasodilation, a neogenesis of microvasculature is activated. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is a highly specific mitogen and inducer of angiogenesis and lymphangiogenesis. HIFs regulate the metabolic and angiogenic activity in endothelial cells under both normal and hypoxic conditions and in diseases that are associated with cardiovascular complications [16]. Multiple publications reported that vascular endothelial growth factor inhibitors lead to hypertension [19,20].

6.4. Mitochondrial responses to long-term ED

Under relatively short-time alterations of energy demands in cells, mitochondria mainly use the fusion-fission mechanism [17,18]. In cell types with mostly uneven oxygen distribution, mitochondria use their motility to reach local areas with a higher oxygen concentration. This strategy is effective in neurons possessing long dendrites and axons. If the total effect provided by these mechanisms, and feed-back mechanisms based on concentrations of ADP/ATP is not able to recover CEB, additional mechanisms become activated. Theoretically, both the hypertrophy and proliferation of existing mitochondria result in growth of $v_s(\tau)$.

6.5. Interim conclusions

Every rate of cell metabolism must be provided with both energy and substrates. Blood flows provided by pressure gradients play an assistant role in transporting of nutrients and oxygen into the cell, and in the removal of unnecessary metabolites from it. Mitochondria synthesize most of the ATP molecules. At the proper concentrations of carbohydrates and oxygen, the total area of the internal membranes of cell mitochondria is the main determinant of the rate of ATP's aerobic synthesis. Under critical lowering of cell metabolism, intermediate agents of two types become accumulating in the cell. Through negative feedback, agents of the first type influence gene expression and regulate ATP synthesis but to a limited extent. Agents of the second type leave the cell and, spreading with fluids, modulate the activity of a functional super-system (FSS) to provide the due metabolism [12]. FSS includes systems of digestion, external respiration, the removal of metabolic wastes, as well as the CVS. The ideal integral effect of such modulation is in restoring the energy balance on the rate of ATP molecules consumption. Enhancing mitochondrial health is emerging as a feasible approach to treat hypertension. The increasing of mean arterial pressure is only one of the ways to provide the integral effect thus OAP's elevation reversible depends on activities of other components of FSS. Structural rearrangements in affected cells are optimal when the proper production capacity of mitochondria is provided. Difficulties on this path lead to a relatively increase of compensator roles of other ways commonly optimizing the cellular metabolism. Problems associated with cytoplasm biochemical purification are another originators of OAP's.

The complex mechanism that uses both the cellular mechanism of reactive adaptation (CMRA) and multicellular mechanisms enhancing the CMRA is schematically illustrated in pic 2. Energy deficit cells (EDC) are activators of multicellular enhancers energy balanced cells (EBC) are only passive users of resources.

Pic.2 A version of the energy mega-system under sustained severe hypoxia caused by circulatory disorders in a big body region.

7. Discussion: accentuation of important nuances

It is well known that human cells permanently die and this does not cause essential biological fluctuations. At first glance, this fact works against the adaptation theory proposed in this paper. However, several nuances of real multicellular life refute this seemingly true misconception.

It is known that an organ consists of different specialized cells. The question is whether every such cell is an elementary functional structure (EFS). If yes, cellular fate could certainly leave its mark on the fate of the organ. In a real multicellular organism (plant or animal), the specialized cell produces its daughter cells and eventually forms a colony of specialized cells (CSC). Namely, CSC is the elementary functional structure (EFS). As a rule, an organ is built of multiple CSCs. Within the given CSC, sister cells are not absolute copies of one another [6]. This is the consequence of temporal instabilities in the physiochemical local environment that originate little structural heterogeneities of cells. In turn, the shape of spatial-temporal characteristics of the entire CSC depends on the statistical dis-

tribution of these heterogeneities. These nuances complicate the effects of cellular CMRA at the scale of CSC. The dynamics of other analogous components of the given organ may have their adaptation trajectories, it becomes clear that the input-output function of such an organ cannot be predicted easily. One can only assert that on the scale of an organ, the dynamics of adaptation are passively formed as the sum of active adaptive changes in its cells plus effects followed by alterations of their numbers. Following this logic, in more complex functional structures of the organism (for example, an anatomical-functional system, a functional system consisting of several anatomical-functional systems, as well as on the scale of the whole organism), the effect of adaptation is also the passive result of the integration of active and passive partial effects.

After understanding the fundamental role of events and causal interconnections between particular components of the general mechanism evolved during long evolution, it is useful to stress four key statements explaining the general vision of the functional super-system that is simultaneously both the material supporter of cells' optimal life and its adjuster under unstable environmental conditions (see pic.3).

Pic.3 Key statements that explain the super-system of cellular life support both adjusting functionally associated organs and the whole organism to endogenous/exogenous changes.

8. Conclusion

In every cell, inevitable destructions of biological macromolecules are the main originators of dangerous ultra-structural degradations. Aerobic cells are armed with intracellular mechanisms actively compensating up to moderate ultra-structural degradations. These mechanisms use multiple negative feedback between cytoplasmic concentrations of interim agents of metabolism on the one hand and expression of genetic sites determining the synthesis of ATP on the other hand. As the compensation is based on additional biosynthesis which requires adequate intracellular assortment and concentration of source chemicals, under sustained and extreme destructive trends, multiple multicellular mechanisms enhance material flows to provide adequate cytoplasmic conditions for the development of compensatory biosynthesis. This is why human biometry (organ's mass, geometry, and sizes, as well as biochemical, biophysical, and physiological features) normally fluctuate or display long-term trends. Cells are the lowest structural-functional units of every multicellular organism that possess active mechanisms for reacting to destruction. Organ-scale and organism-scale adaptive re-structuring is only a passive event resulting from the qualified alterations in cells and changes of cells' number in their colonies. This novel view of an organism's adaptation to external/internal challenges is a basis for proposing medical technologies for outer control of adaptation's trajectory.

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